

Emulating 2D Ice-Sheet Dynamics using Graph Networks

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Abstract

Future sea-level-rise projections remain limited by uncertainty in Antarctic and Greenland ice-sheet evolution. Reducing this uncertainty requires large ensembles of high-resolution simulations, but numerical ice-sheet models are computationally expensive and difficult to scale. Machine-learning emulators offer faster alternatives, yet architectures such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are designed for regular grids and may struggle to represent the heterogeneous geometries and spatially varying dynamics typical of ice-sheet systems. Here, we evaluate MeshGraphNet (MGN) as an emulator for two-dimensional ice-sheet dynamics under limited data and computational resources, using MISMIP+ simulations generated with WAVI. The model predicts ice velocity and thickness through single-step forecasts and autoregressive rollouts, and is compared with CNN and graph convolutional network (GCN) baselines. Although the CNN achieves slightly lower prediction errors on the regular-grid setup, MGN substantially outperforms the GCN, reproduces the main spatiotemporal evolution with good fidelity, and accelerates rollouts by three orders of magnitude relative to WAVI.

Keywords: Ice Sheet Emulation, Machine Learning, Graph Neural Networks

1. Introduction

The dynamics of the Antarctic and Greenland ice sheets are a major source of uncertainty in future sea level rise projections (IPCC 2021; Rignot et al. 2019). Accurately predicting their evolution, along with associated uncertainties, is therefore essential for reliable projections and effective climate adaptation strategies (Church & White 2013; DeConto & Pollard 2016). Uncertainty is typically estimated using ensembles of simulations with varying parameters and forcings (Goelzer et al. 2020). However, traditional ice sheet models based on nonlinear PDEs are computationally expensive and difficult to scale, limiting their use for high-resolution simulations and uncertainty quantification (Greve & Blatter 2009; Pattyn 2017; Aschwanden et al. 2016; Goelzer et al. 2020).

To address these limitations, machine learning (ML) has emerged as a promising complement or alternative to numerical models (Watson-Parris 2021; Van Katwyk et al. 2025; Koo & Rahnemoonfar 2024; Koo & Rahnemoonfar 2025). Statistical surrogate models can approximate com-

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plex physics-based simulations, enabling orders-of-magnitude speedups while maintaining high accuracy (Jouvet et al. 2022). This progress is driven by advances in hardware (GPUs), deep learning architectures, and the increasing availability of high-quality data (Dueben & Bauer 2018; de Burgh-Day & Leeuwenburg 2023).

MGN offers a promising architecture for emulating 2D ice-sheet dynamics because it combines graph-based message passing with mesh-aware spatial representations (Pfaff et al. 2020). As a graph neural network (GNN), MGN is well suited to irregular domains and unstructured meshes, unlike commonly used CNNs, which are naturally tied to regular grids (Jouvet et al. 2022). This is particularly relevant for ice-sheet modelling, where spatial domains are heterogeneous and exhibit localized dynamics, for example near grounding lines (Battaglia et al. 2018; Koo & Rahnemoonfar 2025). By capturing local interactions in mesh-based simulations, MGN provides a physically intuitive framework for modelling spatiotemporal evolution. It extends standard GNNs by incorporating edge features and predicting time derivatives that are integrated over time, enabling dynamic simulations while respecting mesh connectivity (Pfaff et al. 2020; Sanchez-Gonzalez et al. 2018).

The objective of this study is to evaluate MeshGraphNet as an emulator for ice sheet dynamics under limited data and computational constraints. The model is assessed on the standardized MISIMIP+ setup (Cornford et al. 2020), focusing on its ability to reproduce spatial and temporal evolution through both short-term and long-term predictions. In addition to predictive accuracy, computational efficiency is qualitatively evaluated during training and inference (Pfaff et al. 2020). The results highlight the strengths and limitations of MeshGraphNet and its potential as a scalable tool for ice sheet modeling.

2. Methods

This section presents the methodology for developing and evaluating a MGN-based emulator of ice sheet dynamics. Section 2.1 introduces the model architecture and Section 2.2 describes the data generation and training setup.

2.1. Model Description

MGN is a graph neural network designed for modeling physical systems on irregular spatial grids (Pfaff et al. 2020). It operates on a dynamic mesh representation of the physical state, where nodes and edges encode physical and spatial information. The model follows an encoder–processor–decoder architecture (Figure 1).

The system state at time t is represented as a mesh $M^t = (V, E)$, where V is the set of nodes and E the set of edges. Each node $i \in V$ has coordinates $\mathbf{r}_i \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and physical variables \mathbf{q}_i . Each edge $(i, j) \in E$ encodes the relative displacement $\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i$ and its norm, capturing local geometric relationships. The primary node variables are vertically integrated ice velocities (longitudinal and lateral) and ice thickness. Additional variables are also used to provide context, as shown in Figure 1.

The encoder maps node and edge features to latent embeddings, transforming physical variables

Figure 1: Schematic overview of the MGN architecture, consisting of an encoder, processor and decoder, and dataflow. Adapted from Dwivedi et al. (2020).

\mathbf{q}_i into node embeddings \mathbf{x}_i and relative positional features into edge embeddings \mathbf{e}_{ij} using multi-layer perceptrons (MLPs).

The processor performs L rounds of message passing to propagate information across the mesh. Here, $\mathcal{N}(i)$ denotes the neighbors of node i , and f^M, f^V are learnable MLPs. At each layer:

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij}^{t+1} = f^M([\mathbf{x}_i^t \parallel \mathbf{x}_j^t \parallel \mathbf{e}_{ij}^t]) + \mathbf{e}_{ij}^t,$$

$$\mathbf{m}_i = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}(i)} \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{t+1}, \quad \mathbf{x}_i^{t+1} = f^V([\mathbf{x}_i^t \parallel \mathbf{m}_i]) + \mathbf{x}_i^t,$$

where \mathbf{m}_i is the aggregated message.

The decoder maps the final embeddings \mathbf{x}_i^L to physical predictions. Instead of absolute values, the model predicts normalized time derivatives, which are integrated using a forward Euler step:

$$\hat{\mathbf{q}}_i^{t+1} = \mathbf{q}_i^t + \delta_V(\mathbf{x}_i^L) \Delta t.$$

During rollout, predicted states are recursively fed back as inputs, enabling autoregressive simulation over long time horizons. For ice velocities and thickness, derivatives are integrated, while derived quantities such as surface elevation and height above flotation (HAF) are computed diagnostically using the predicted variables and the water/ice densities. Bed elevation is fixed, and forcing variables such as surface mass balance (SMB) and basal melt are prescribed.

The original MeshGraphNet distinguishes between *world space* and *mesh space* to allow long-range interactions (Pfaff et al. 2020). For 2D ice sheet modeling, this distinction is omitted, and only local mesh connectivity is used. Adaptive remeshing strategies are also excluded.

2.2. Data and Training Setup

Simulation data is generated using the standardized MISIMIP+ framework (Cornford et al. 2020), providing a controlled setting for ice sheet dynamics. Data are produced with the Wavelet-based Adaptive-grid Vertically-integrated Ice (WAVI) model (Bradley et al. 2024), a two-dimensional depth-integrated model combining shallow-ice and shallow-shelf approximations (Greve & Blatter 2009; Lipscomb et al. 2018). Simulations are performed on a 640 km \times 80 km domain with 8 km resolution.

First, 64 steady-state spin-up simulations are generated using latin hypercube sampling over the forcing parameters: surface mass balance (SMB) and a basal melt tuning parameter γ_T . From each spin-up simulation, ten transient trajectories of 100 years are generated by evolving SMB and γ_T using a temporally correlated AR(1) random process within prescribed bounds (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos 2021), with SMB varying between 0.25 m/yr and 0.53 m/yr and γ_T between 0.5×10^{-5} and 5×10^{-5} [-]. During these transient simulations, sufficient Picard iterations, with a maximum of 100 iterations per timestep, are performed to ensure numerical stability. Since MGN operates on triangular meshes, the regular grid output is converted using Delaunay triangulation (Persson & Strang 2004; Shewchuk 1996).

After splitting the dataset at the trajectory level into 80/10/10% training, validation, and test sets, the model is trained in a supervised manner to predict the normalized first-order time derivatives of the physical variables. Inputs and targets are normalized using global statistics from the training dataset. Optimization is performed using the Adam optimizer with a fixed learning rate of 10^{-4} , and RMSE is used as the loss function. All models are implemented in the PyTorch framework and trained using CUDA acceleration on an NVIDIA RTX PRO 1000 Blackwell Generation Laptop GPU, with a fixed training time of 1 hour for each model.

During testing, the model is evaluated on both single-step predictions, where the ground truth is used as input at each timestep, and autoregressive rollouts, where the predicted outputs are recursively fed back as inputs. In addition, inference time is measured to assess computational efficiency.

The MGN uses 64 hidden features, three message-passing steps, and two hidden layers in each MLP. It can be viewed as a specialized graph-convolutional model: it performs graph-based message passing, but extends the basic GCN with edge features and learned encoder-processor-decoder components. CNN and GCN baselines are included for comparison. Like the MGN, both baselines use only node features and predict finite-step rates of change of the target variables. The CNN consists of five padded convolutional layers, preserving the spatial domain, with 60 hidden channels. The GCN follows Kipf and Welling (2017), using four graph-convolutional layers to limit oversmoothing and a hidden dimension of 220. Accordingly, all three models have approximately 100,000 learnable parameters.

3. Results

As our objective is to develop a fast, high-fidelity emulator, we evaluate the models based on both predictive performance and inference speed. Table 1 summarizes the RMSE (normalized), MAE (physical units) for the three main variables and inference time for the MGN and the baseline models, both for single-step predictions and rollouts.

3.1. Aggregated Results

The MGN is outperformed by the CNN for most metrics, but only by relatively small margins. This is expected, since CNNs are specifically designed for regular grid-structured data and can exploit highly optimized dense convolution operations on GPUs, making them both accurate and efficient in this setting (Bronstein et al. 2021; Chetlur et al. 2014). In contrast, GNNs such as MGN and GCN are designed for graph- or mesh-based domains, including irregular spatial discretizations, and rely on sparse message-passing operations that are generally less efficient on GPUs than dense convolutions (Battaglia et al. 2018; Pfaff et al. 2020; Wang et al. 2023). Despite this disadvantage in the present setup, where only regular grids are used, the MGN achieves performance close to that of the CNN and even outperforms it for the single-step prediction of ice thickness h , the main variable of interest. The MGN is also substantially faster than WAVI, requiring only 0.17 s per 100-step rollout on average, corresponding to a speedup of three orders of magnitude. In terms of speed, notice that the rollout times are slightly lower. This is likely caused by reduced per-step overhead, since the rollout reuses and updates a trajectory state in memory instead of repeatedly processing independent timestep samples through the data-loading pipeline.

Metric	Single-step prediction			Autoregressive rollout			WAVI
	MGN	CNN	GCN	MGN	CNN	GCN	
RMSE	0.295	0.261	0.587	0.570	0.421	1.037	--
MAE u	0.051	0.046	0.075	1.700	1.778	2.572	--
MAE v	0.013	0.011	0.031	0.402	0.217	1.094	--
MAE h	0.046	0.061	0.223	2.175	1.873	8.972	--
Time (s)	0.18	0.08	0.27	0.17	0.07	0.25	172
	± 0.015	± 0.007	± 0.014	± 0.013	± 0.007	± 0.026	± 104

Table 1: Comparison of single-step prediction and autoregressive rollout performance on the test set, containing 64 trajectories. The table reports RMSE together with MAE for the velocity components (m yr^{-1}) and ice thickness h (m), as well as mean inference time per trajectory or rollout with their uncertainty. The last column includes the average time needed to generate one trajectory using the WAVI model.

The benefit of the MGN becomes clearer when compared with the simpler GCN. The MGN performs substantially better across all metrics, indicating that its accuracy is not merely due to using graph connectivity. Instead, the improvement is likely due to the use of edge information, which provides additional geometric and spatial context, and to the encoder-processor-decoder architecture, which enables richer node and edge representations (Battaglia et al. 2018; Sanchez-Gonzalez et al. 2018; Pfaff et al. 2020).

3.2. Spatiotemporal Fidelity

In this subsection, we examine the model behavior in more detail using a representative trajectory. First, we assess the spatial structure of the predicted ice-thickness field after 50 years (Figure 2). Second, we analyze the temporal evolution at three spatial locations corresponding to distinct dynamical regimes: the ice-sheet interior, the grounding line, and the ice shelf (Figure 3). Although these visualizations are based on a single trajectory, they provide additional insight beyond the aggregate metrics.

Figure 2: Spatial evaluation of the MGN prediction after 50 years. The figure shows the predicted ice thickness, the ground truth, and the corresponding error field. The grounding line is shown in black.

After 50 years, the MGN seems to preserve the large-scale spatial structure of the ice-thickness field well (Figure 2). However, the spatial error field reveals systematic deviations. In particular, the MGN underestimates ice-thickness growth across the ice sheet, which is consistent with the negative bias visible in the predicted temporal changes in Figure 3. Errors are generally modest in the ice-sheet interior, where the dynamics evolve relatively smoothly, but become larger and more spatially irregular near the ice-shelf margins and grounding-line region, where the dynamics are more complex and nonlinear (Pattyn 2017; Cornford et al. 2020). These larger errors may be partly related to physically inconsistent nodes in these dynamically complex regions, potentially arising from the minimum ice-thickness threshold of 50 m imposed in the WAVI model.

The temporal rollouts further highlight the differences between the models (Figure 3). They reveal gradual error accumulation during autoregressive rollout, where small prediction biases compound over time, a common challenge in recursive time-series prediction (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos 2021). At location A, in the ice-sheet interior, the MGN reproduces the overall temporal evolution well, but shows a persistent negative bias that leads to a gradual deviation from the ground truth over time. Near the grounding line at location B, the agreement is weaker. The MGN predictions are noticeably smoother and less variable than the reference trajectory, suggesting that the model does not fully capture the local dynamics in this region. A similar loss of variability is also visible in the baseline models, indicating that the grounding-line region is particularly challenging to emulate. At location C, on the ice shelf, the target signal is more oscillatory. The MGN captures this oscillatory behaviour reasonably well, although the CNN follows the ground truth more closely.

Figure 3: Temporal rollouts at three representative locations: the ice-sheet interior, grounding line, and ice shelf. MGN predictions are compared with the ground truth and baseline models. The first column shows absolute values during the rollout, while the second column shows the predicted changes over time.

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the potential of MGN as an efficient emulator for 2D ice-sheet dynamics under limited data and computational constraints. Using the MISMIP+ framework, the MGN reproduced the main spatial and temporal evolution of the simulated ice sheet with good fidelity. Although the CNN achieved slightly better aggregate performance, this is expected because the experiments were conducted on regular grids, where a CNN architecture has a natural advantage.

Compared with the simpler GCN baseline, the MGN performed substantially better across all metrics, highlighting the importance of edge information and the encoder-processor-decoder message-passing architecture. The MGN also achieved a large speedup of more than three orders of magnitude relative to WAVI. These results show that the MGN provides a strong graph-based surrogate that combines accuracy, efficiency, and flexibility for mesh-based ice-sheet emulation.

The rollout analysis also revealed several limitations. Small systematic biases accumulated over time, reducing stability over longer prediction horizons, while the largest errors occurred near the grounding line and ice-shelf margins, where the dynamics are more complex. Future work should therefore focus on evaluating the model on irregular or adaptive meshes, reducing bias accumulation during rollout, and improving robustness in dynamically challenging regions.

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